

Development of a methodology for the application of vinyl paint as a radon mitigation barrier for interior spaces

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ABSTRACT

Radon gas is a radioactive gas produced by the decay of uranium and radium, which occur naturally in soil and rock. Radon gas can migrate into buildings from the ground and, to a lesser extent, from building materials such as bricks, granite and concrete. The accumulation of radon indoors can pose a significant health risk, as its inhalation can damage lung tissue, making it the second leading cause of lung cancer after smoking. In 2013, the European Union adopted Directive 2013/59/EURATOM, establishing an average reference level of 300 Bq/m³ in inhabited areas and the obligation to measure building radon concentrations. In Spain, Royal Decree 732/2019 adapts this directive and establishes specific requirements to protect people from radon exposure. The main mitigation measures include sealing cracks, natural or forced ventilation, sub-slab depressurisation and installing radon barriers. Although current measures are effective, research continues into new solutions to further reduce indoor radon levels. This work focuses on developing an evaluating a methodology for applying a commercially available regular indoor paint to ensure that it can be used as an anti-radon barrier in walls. The results show that a vinyl paint can be used to mitigate radon in indoor spaces reaching a radon concentration reduction percentage of 82.25 %, and a diffusion coefficient of 7.48·10⁻¹¹ m²/s. The increase in the number of coats is proportional to the effectiveness for radon reduction per unit thickness, with the best results achieved at thicknesses of 90 µm. These results open the possibility of using decorative surface coatings to mitigate the access of radon gas indoors in a simple, accessible and low-cost way that contributes to improving indoor air quality and reducing the impact of radon gas on people's health.

1. Introduction

Radon-222 is produced naturally by the decay of radium-226 contained in rocks, which in turn comes from the decay chain of uranium-238 present in rocks and soil. This gas emanates from the ground and can penetrate buildings or, to a lesser extent, can be exhaled by some commonly used building materials such as brick, granite, cement, gravel or plaster (Pacheco-Torgal, 2012). The accumulation of radon in indoor spaces can pose a risk to human health, as radon can be inhaled, and the radioactive particles resulting from its decay can damage lung tissue. In 1986, the World Health Organization (WHO) classified radon as a carcinogen, and it is now the second leading cause of lung cancer after smoking (World Health Organization, 2009).

In 2013, the European Union, recognising the health risks associated with radon, approved a new directive (2013/59/EURATOM). This directive established an average reference level in habitable places of 300 Bq/m³ and the obligation to measure radon concentration and

adopt measures to limit the penetration of the gas in buildings (Council of the European Union, 2013). This regulatory framework provides a clear radon mitigation standard, ensuring the safety of indoor spaces. Under this framework, the Spanish government, through Royal Decree 732/2019 (Spanish Ministry of Housing and Urban Agenda, 2019), which amends the Spanish Technical Building Code, establishes the requisite standards for the protection of people in buildings, and the reference level that has been adapted to align with the EURATOM Directive.

The current mitigation measures are designed to prevent radon from entering the building or to decrease the radon concentration in the air. Among the most used techniques are crack sealing, natural/forced ventilation or soil depressurisation. However, the most important technique for new buildings is the installation of barriers on the ground (Daoud & Renken K.J., 2001; Jiránek and Hulka, 2001). In accordance with the Spanish Technical Building Code, a radon barrier that limits the risk of exposure of users to high radon concentrations that exhale from

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the ground should have the following characteristics: it should be continuous, watertight, and have the same useful life as the building. Furthermore, radon barrier on the ground should generally have a minimum thickness of 2 mm and a radon diffusion coefficient of less than 10^{-11} m²/s, however if the barrier does not meet these characteristics, the thickness could be recalculated according to the formula specified in the Technical Building Code (Spanish Ministry of Housing and Urban Agenda, 2019). The radon diffusion coefficient is the property that defines the transport of radon through the material and can, therefore, be used to determine the effectiveness of a material as a radon barrier (Jiránek M. et al., 2012).

Nevertheless, the regulatory recommendations are specific to barriers implemented in foundations, while for interiors, there is a need to investigate new solutions to reduce indoor radon concentrations below the established limits. Several studies have investigated the efficacy of employing different coating materials, such as paints or coatings, to assess their capacity to reduce indoor radon concentrations.

There are references of epoxy or polyurethane paints with low diffusion coefficients (ranging from $1.3 \cdot 10^{-11}$ to $4.6 \cdot 10^{-12}$ m²/s) that act as impermeable barriers to radon (Jiránek and Svoboda, 2017), epoxy paints with hardener, for which its application in two coats has been shown to achieve a reduction in indoor radon concentration of 80 % (Husham et al., 2013) or the use of interior and exterior paints that, after the application of three coats of paint directly on the radon emanation media, can achieve a reduction of radon exhalation in the order of 25 % (Singh et al., 2005). An anti-radon coating consisting of three coats (filler, primer and top coat) has also shown a reduction in radon concentration of 99.85 % (Gao et al., 2008). In addition, anti-radon paints based on graphene particles (Barpimo Coatings, 2023) have recently been commercialised for use on indoor floors and walls in areas where radon concentration exceeds 300 Bq/m³, as well as for the waterproofing of terraces, roofs and roof terraces. The diffusion coefficient of this anti-radon paint is $(2.1 \pm 0.6) \cdot 10^{-12}$ m²/s. Table 1 summarises the main characteristics of the coating materials studied to mitigate radon gas according to various literature sources.

These coating materials act as a barrier that hinders the gas diffusion from the building materials. The effectiveness of these materials can be influenced by several factors, including the chemical composition of the paint, the thickness of the coating applied and the compatibility with the building element on which it is applied (Singh et al., 2005).

This paper focuses on the study of the use of commercial paints as indoor anti-radon barriers. For this purpose, a paint application methodology has been developed, and its radon mitigation capacity has been evaluated. Paint application can be a simple, easily accessible, and low-cost alternative to mitigate radon exhaled from building materials. Furthermore, it is compatible with most interior wall and ceiling building materials used in existing buildings. While traditional solutions (crack sealing, controlled ventilation) remain indispensable for reducing radon concentration to the legal limit in indoor spaces, applying particular coatings, such as indoor commercial paint, can be an effective

strategy for existing buildings.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Experimental set-up

The experimental set-up used for the measurement of the radon diffusion coefficient has been designed according to ISO/TS 11665-13:2017 (International Organization for Standardization, 2017) previously used by (Ruvira et al., 2022). The set-up consists of two sealed chambers (source chamber and receiver chamber) made of AISI 316L stainless steel with a thickness of 2 mm. The volume of each chamber is 0.801 L, and the test area is 78.5 cm². The radon source, a sealed pitchblende stone with an activity of 1.469 kBq, is inserted into the source chamber, and the sample to be tested is placed between the two chambers, which are sealed with O-rings and bolts.

Radon is extracted from the chambers and passed through a desiccant unit (drierite) to maintain the relative humidity below 10 %, reaching the RAD7 continuous detectors (DurrIDGE), where the radon concentration is recorded every half hour for 48 h. The air extracted from the chambers for radon concentration analysis is reintroduced into the chamber, thus maintaining a closed cycle. All devices in the experimental set-up are connected to each other with 1.41 mm and 1.81 mm thick vinyl tubing. A detailed diagram of the experimental set-up used is shown below in Fig. 1.

2.2. Samples

In order to study the effect of the paint as an indoor anti-radon barrier, three neutral substrates (filter paper, non-woven fabric, and greaseproof paper) were tested to select the one with the least resistance to radon passage. For each neutral substrate, the percentage reduction in radon concentration and the diffusion coefficient were estimated according to the calculation method detailed in section 2.4. The samples have a thickness of 51.25 μm (greaseproof paper), 154.00 μm (non-woven fabric) and 182.50 μm (filter paper), measured with a micrometre (model 3006 from Baxlo Precision, with an accuracy of 10 μm). The thickness is calculated as the average of 8 measurements at different points on the sample, as shown in Fig. 2.

For the selection of the neutral substrates, it has been considered that.

- Filter paper is made of high-quality cellulose fibres, which guarantees a high level of absorption.
- The non-woven fabric is a 100 % synthetic material made of high-density polyethylene fibres, making it water-resistant.
- Greaseproof paper is a cellulose paper that has undergone chemical treatment to cover the pores, making it a material with high resistance to high temperatures, impermeable, and non-stick.

Table 1

Main characteristics of different coating materials according to various bibliographical sources.

Coating	Radon diffusion coefficient (m ² /s)	Radon reduction concentration (%)	Radon reduction exhalation (%)	Application	Reference
Epoxy paint	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-12}$ to $4.3 \cdot 10^{-12}$	–	–	–	Jiránek and Svoboda (2017)
Polyurethane paints	$1.4 \cdot 10^{-12}$ to $1.3 \cdot 10^{-11}$	–	–	–	Jiránek and Svoboda (2017)
High-performance epoxy resin	–	80.00	–	Two coats of paint mixed with the hardener	Husham et al. (2013)
Interior and exterior paints	–	–	25.00	Three coats of paint	Singh et al. (2005)
Anti-radon coating	–	99.85	–	Coating consisting of three coats (filler, primer and top coat)	Gao et al. (2008)
Anti-radon paints	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-12}$ to $2.7 \cdot 10^{-12}$	–	–	Paint based on graphene particles	Barpimo Coatings (2023)

Fig. 1. Radon diffusion coefficient experimental set-up.

Fig. 2. Diagram of the eight measurement points used to calculate the average thickness of the sample.

After, the commercial paint was applied to these substrates according to the painting methodology described in section 2.3.

The paint used is a commercial water-based vinyl plastic paint for indoor use with a density of 1.52 ± 0.07 g/ml. Paints based on vinyl resins are characterised by their high resistance to humidity, and by their flexibility and chemical resistance.

Additionally, a commercially available anti-radon paint with graphene nanoparticles and a density of 1.30 ± 0.05 g/ml was employed as a control to facilitate a comparison of the results obtained in the radon diffusion coefficient estimation tests. The diffusion coefficient of the anti-radon paint provided by the manufacturer is $(2.1 \pm 0.6) \cdot 10^{-12}$ m²/s.

A characterisation of the surface finish of the samples with paint was carried out using a Leica Microsystems MZ APO magnifying glass. In addition, the profile of the neutral support samples with paint was characterised using a field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM), model ULTRA 55 from Zeiss and Oxford Instruments. Both instruments are available at the Electron Microscopy Service of the Polytechnic University of Valencia.

2.3. Painting methodology

A methodology has been developed which consists of the application of several coats of paint on the chosen neutral support. The first coat of paint was diluted with 20 % distilled water before application. Diluted

paint was stirred with a glass stirring rod to achieve a homogeneous mixture. The first coat of paint is then applied to the substrate using a brush until a uniform surface is obtained. After, the sample is left to dry in the lab oven (model UN75, Memmert brand) at 36 °C for 24 h to ensure good drying. The same procedure is carried out when several coats of paint are applied, if necessary, but using undiluted paint.

Fig. 3 illustrates a sample preparation process block chart following the developed painting methodology.

2.4. Method of calculation of the diffusion coefficient

Each sample has been tested two times, and the results shown in the following section are calculated from the average of the experimental

Fig. 3. Block chart of the sample preparation process according to the developed methodology of painting and measuring radon concentrations.

Table 2

Minimum radon resistance values $R_{Rn,min}$ of barriers depending on radon concentration and building characteristics based on the equation from (Jiránek, 2017).

	Minimum Radon resistance (Ms/m)		
	Low radon area	Medium radon area	High radon area
A naturally ventilated building without a basement, with habitable rooms on the ground floor	17	50	100
A building on row 1, with passive subsoil or air gap ventilation	10	33	67
A building on row 1, with mechanical ventilation of habitable rooms, or with active subsoil or air gap ventilation	5	17	33
A naturally ventilated building with habitable rooms in the basement	33	100	200
A building on row 4, with passive subsoil or air gap ventilation	20	67	134
A building on row 4, with mechanical ventilation of habitable rooms, or with active subsoil or air gap ventilation	10	33	67

values. First, the average concentrations of both chambers during the last 24 h of the test are calculated, according to previous work by (Ruvira et al., 2022). These values are used to calculate the percentage reduction in radon concentration:

$$Reduction(\%) = \frac{C_{SC} - C_{RC}}{C_{SC}} \cdot 100 \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Where C_{SC} and C_{RC} are the average radon concentrations in the source and receiver chambers during the last 24 h (Bq/m^3), respectively.

The radon diffusion coefficient, D (m^2/s), for each sample has been calculated based on method A defined in ISO/TS 11665-13:2017 (International Organization for Standardization, 2017) for determining the radon diffusion coefficient during the phase non-stationary radon diffusion. The radon diffusion coefficient is determined by solving the equations contained in the standard using an iterative procedure.

Following the calculation of the radon diffusion coefficient, the radon diffusion length, l (m), can be determined. This is defined as the distance crossed by radon due to diffusion in which the activity is reduced by 'e' times as a result of decay. The diffusion length of radon can be expressed by Equation (2):

$$l = (D/\lambda)^{1/2} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Where λ (s^{-1}) is the radon decay constant ($2.1 \cdot 10^{-6} s^{-1}$).

2.5. Evaluation of the effectiveness of the barrier

Given that there are no established standards for indoor barriers, in order to evaluate the effectiveness of the barrier, the value indicated in the CTE (Spanish Technical Building Code) for outdoor barriers (Spanish Ministry of Housing and Urban Agenda, 2019), which establishes a radon diffusion coefficient of less than $10^{-11} m^2/s$, is taken as a reference for the comparison of the results obtained. The percentage reduction in radon concentration, as described in Equation (1), shall also be considered.

To also assess the suitability of the samples to act as a radon barrier, the radon resistance of the materials is calculated as (Jiránek and Svoboda, 2017):

$$R_{Rn} (Ms/m) = \frac{\sinh d/l}{\lambda \cdot l} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Where d (m) is the thickness of the sample.

According to (Jiránek, 2017), there is a minimum radon resistance that must be considered to ensure that the material provides a good radon barrier. This minimum resistance R_{Rn} depends on the characteristics of the building and the radon concentration of the soil, as shown in

Table 3

Parameters obtained in calculating the radon diffusion coefficient of different types of neutral substrates.

Substrate	Thickness (μm)	Radon concentration reduction (%)	Radon resistance (Ms/m)	l (mm)	D (m^2/s)
Filter paper	182.50 \pm 10.00	9.55	0.08	32.29	(2.19 \pm 0.16) $\cdot 10^{-9}$
Non-woven fabric	154.00 \pm 10.90	10.76	0.09	28.62	(1.72 \pm 0.14) $\cdot 10^{-9}$
Greaseproof paper	51.25 \pm 2.32	48.73	0.94	5.08	(5.43 \pm 0.14) $\cdot 10^{-11}$

Table 2, whose values have been calculated applying Spanish legislation.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Substrate

Table 3 shows the diffusion coefficient test results for the paint substrates. These results will be used to select the substrate which offers the least resistance to the passage of radon through it, thus providing a lower percentage reduction in the concentration of radon gas and a higher diffusion coefficient.

As can be seen in Table 3, the substrate with the lowest radon concentration reduction percentage and the highest diffusion coefficient is filter paper. Moreover, this material has a high paint absorption capacity and is an inert substrate, which makes it the best candidate for the homogeneous application of the paint in the following test.

On the other hand, both non-woven fabric and greaseproof paper have higher radon reduction percentages and lower radon diffusion coefficients, which implies that they can act as an anti-radon barrier.

Since the substrate is intended to be used as a support for the paint to assess the net effect of the paint, the substrate selected for the tests will ultimately be filter paper.

3.2. Painting

3.2.1. Results of diffusion coefficient test

a) Results for one coat

Tests were conducted by applying one coat of paint to be tested on the filter paper as a neutral substrate. After, the diffusion coefficient test of the sample was performed following the methodology described in section 2.1. Results are shown in Fig. 4.

The percentage reduction in the radon concentration, radon resistance of the material, and the length and radon diffusion coefficient through the sample were calculated according to section 2.4.

Radon diffusion coefficient tests were performed in duplicate for each sample. Table 4 shows the average value and deviation of the C_{SC} and C_{RC} concentrations. However, the reduction is calculated based on the average value. Table 4 presents the results obtained with one coat.

The sample with one coat of commercial paint shows a low radon reduction percentage (10.17 %), reaching very similar concentrations in the source and receiver chambers (367.70 kBq/m^3 and 330.29 kBq/m^3 , respectively). Furthermore, its radon resistance is very low, around 0.10 Ms/m, which indicates that it does not reach the minimum radon

Fig. 4. Evolution of radon concentration in the source chamber (solid line) and the receiver chamber (dashed line) when one coat of commercial paint and one coat of anti-radon paint are applied on filter paper.

resistance required for the most favourable case described in Table 2.

As can be seen, the radon diffusion coefficient value for the commercial paint ($1.93 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$) is considerably lower than the limit established in the CTE, indicating that a single coat of paint would not be effective as a radon barrier. Moreover, the radon diffusion length (l), with a value of 30.32 mm, is observed to be greater than the thickness (d) of the sample, which means that the radon can pass through the paint coat before disintegrating.

On the other hand, the application of an anti-radon paint achieves a radon concentration reduction percentage of 98.00 %, and a low diffusion coefficient below the limit value set by the CTE. In this case, the

sample has a medium radon resistance, with a value of 34.32 Ms/m, which indicates that it could be used in some of the cases listed in Table 2.

b) Two and three coats of painting

It was decided to continue the tests by applying a second and third coat of undiluted paint over the first coat diluted. Results of the measurement of radon concentrations in the chambers for the two coats sample and the three coats sample are shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 illustrates the evolution of the concentration in the source and

Table 4

Parameters obtained in the calculation of the radon diffusion coefficient for a diluted coat of anti-radon paint and a diluted coat of commercial vinyl paint, both paints applied on filter paper.

Paint	Average C_{sc} (kBq/m ³)	Average C_{rc} (kBq/m ³)	Reduction (%)	Resistance (Ms/m)	d (μm)	l (mm)	D (m ² /s)
Commercial paint one coat	367.70 ± 30.06	330.29 ± 27.06	10.17	0.10	197.81 ± 10.54	30.32	$(1.93 \pm 0.11) \cdot 10^{-9}$
Anti-radon paint one coat	693.44 ± 45.30	13.86 ± 3.62	98.00	34.32	207.81 ± 8.16	1.70	$(6.07 \pm 0.03) \cdot 10^{-12}$

Fig. 5. Evolution of radon concentration in the source chamber (solid line) and the receiver chamber (dashed line) when two and three coats of commercial paint and two and three coats of anti-radon paint are applied on filter paper.

Table 5

Parameters obtained in the calculation of the radon diffusion coefficient for two and three coats of anti-radon paint and two and three coats of commercial vinyl paint, both paints applied on filter paper.

Coats	Average C_{SC} (kBq/m ³)	Average C_{RC} (kBq/m ³)	Reduction (%)	Resistance (Ms/m)	d (μm)	l (mm)	D (m ² /s)
Commercial paint two coats	362.04 ± 28.58	302.08 ± 25.59	16.56	0.19	222.50 ± 11.64	23.90	(1.20 ± 0.05) · 10 ⁻⁹
Anti-radon paint two coats	681.83 ± 39.81	6.83 ± 1.76	99.00	68.32	242.50 ± 10.65	1.30	(3.57 ± 0.02) · 10 ⁻¹²
Commercial paint three coats	468.64 ± 18.68	178.39 ± 23.17	61.93	1.44	256.72 ± 9.47	9.21	(1.78 ± 0.04) · 10 ⁻¹⁰
Anti-radon paint three coats	698.23 ± 35.26	7.41 ± 1.55	98.94	66.44	256.25 ± 8.85	1.36	(3.88 ± 0.07) · 10 ⁻¹²

receiver chambers when two and three coats of the two paints tested (commercial paint and anti-radon paint) are applied over one diluted coat of paint. In the case of the commercial vinyl plastic paint, when two coats are applied, very similar concentrations are achieved between the two chambers, 360 kBq/m³ in the source chamber and 300 kBq/m³ in the receiver chamber, indicating a low percentage reduction in radon concentration. However, for the sample with three coats, a larger difference between the recorded concentrations is observed, being 460 kBq/m³ in the source chamber and 180 kBq/m³ in the receiver chamber. For the anti-radon paint, like when one diluted coat was applied, the concentration recorded in the source chamber is close to 700 kBq/m³, while concentrations in the receiver chamber are below 10 kBq/m³.

The percentage reduction in the radon concentration, radon resistance of the material, and the length and radon diffusion coefficient through the sample were calculated according to section 2.4. Table 5 presents the results obtained with two and three coats for commercial paint and anti-radon paint.

The sample of two coats of commercial paint shows similar results to the sample of one diluted coat, with a low percentage of reduction (16.56 %) and a low radon resistance (0.19 Ms/m). Applying one or two coats of commercial paint on the substrate does not represent an improvement in radon shielding, given that the filter paper (neutral substrate) itself presents a radon reduction percentage of 9.55 % and a radon resistance of 0.08 Ms/m.

As with the sample of one coat, the value of diffusion coefficient obtained for the sample of two coats of commercial paint (1.20 · 10⁻⁹ m²/s) is considerably lower than the limit established in the CTE. However, for the sample of three coats, a lower diffusion coefficient is obtained, which approaches the established limit. Nevertheless, it must be noted that the effectiveness of the material is still not sufficient to act as an

anti-radon barrier. With regard to the diffusion length of radon, in both cases, values greater than the thickness of the sample are obtained.

However, it is observed that when a third coat of commercial paint is applied, improved results are obtained regarding percentage reduction in radon concentration, achieving a 61.93 % reduction. In the case of anti-radon paint, the application of a second and third coat has very similar results to the application of one diluted coat, with reduction percentages greater than 98.00 %, as well as diffusion coefficients below the limit established by the CTE and close to the coefficient value provided by the manufacturer of (2.1 ± 0.6) · 10⁻¹² m²/s.

Considering the results obtained for of anti-radon paint, it can be stated that the addition of 2 coats of undiluted paint on top of the initial diluted coat, improves radon mitigation, achieving a high radon resistance value, reaching 68.32 Ms/m. This value meets the minimum requirements for radon barriers in most of the cases listed in Table 2.

c) Fourth and fifth coat

It was decided to continue with the test. For this reason, a fourth and fifth coats of commercial paint were added to determine the effect it had on the reduction of radon concentration and radon diffusion coefficient.

Fig. 6 shows the evolution of the radon concentration in the source and receiver chambers when four and five coats of commercial paint are applied to the neutral substrate, where there is a greater difference in concentration between the two chambers. In the source chamber, concentrations between 500 and 600 kBq/m³ are reached, while in the receiver chamber, concentrations below 200 kBq/m³ are obtained. The difference in concentration between the two chambers is remarkable when four coats of paint are applied, where the source chamber reaches almost 600 kBq/m³ while the concentration in the receiver chamber is

Fig. 6. Evolution of radon concentration in the source chamber (solid line) and the receiver chamber (dashed line) when four and five coats of commercial paint are applied on filter paper.

Table 6

Parameters obtained in the calculation of the radon diffusion coefficient for four and five coats of commercial vinyl paint applied on filter paper.

Coats	Average C_{SC} (kBq/m ³)	Average C_{RC} (kBq/m ³)	Reduction (%)	Resistance (Ms/m)	d (μm)	l (mm)	D (m ² /s)
Commercial paint four coats	543.09 ± 24.61	96.39 ± 17.58	82.25	3.64	272.50 ± 10.55	5.97	(7.48 ± 0.10) · 10 ⁻¹¹
Commercial paint five coats	486.56 ± 27.71	164.71 ± 26.16	66.15	1.64	283.75 ± 14.41	9.08	(1.73 ± 0.03) · 10 ⁻¹⁰

Table 7

Parameters obtained in the calculation of the effectiveness per unit thickness for a diluted coat of anti-radon paint and a diluted coat of commercial vinyl paint, both paints applied on filter paper.

Paint	Net paint layer thickness (μm)	Net radon reduction (%)	Effectiveness per unit thickness
Commercial paint one coat	15.31 ± 14.53	0.62	4.05
Commercial paint two coats	40.00 ± 15.35	7.01	17.53
Commercial paint three coats	74.22 ± 13.77	52.38	70.58
Commercial paint four coats	90.00 ± 14.54	72.70	80.78
Commercial paint five coats	101.25 ± 17.54	56.60	55.90
Anti-radon paint one coat (control)	25.31 ± 12.91	88.45	349.43

slightly above 100 kBq/m³.

In this case, the percentage reduction in radon concentration, the radon resistance of the material, as well as the length and the radon diffusion coefficient through the sample have been calculated as in the previous cases, according to section 2.4.

The results in Table 6 show that the sample with four coats of paint is the most effective for radon mitigation, with a reduction in concentration of 82.25 %, which is approximately 20 % higher than the reduction observed for the sample with three coats of paint. A significant increase in radon resistance is also observed, reaching values of 3.64 Ms/m, more than double that of the previously samples tested; however, the minimum radon resistance required for the most favourable case describe in Table 2 has still not been achieved. In addition, the lowest values are obtained for the radon diffusion coefficient and the radon diffusion length, which reach 7.48 · 10⁻¹¹ m²/s and 5.97 mm, respectively. Furthermore, the diffusion coefficient values obtained are close to the values reported by (Jiránek and Svoboda, 2017) for polyurethane paints, with estimated coefficients of 1.3 · 10⁻¹¹ m²/s.

Finally, when a fifth coat of paint was applied, the results worsened, with a decrease in the percentage reduction (66.15 %) and radon resistance (1.64 Ms/m) compared to the sample with four coats of paint. There is also an increase in the diffusion length (9.08 mm) and the radon diffusion coefficient (1.73 · 10⁻¹⁰ m²/s). This may be due to the amount of paint applied to the substrate was excessive, making the sample too rigid and, at the same time, fragile, resulting in the appearance of microcracks in the surface finish of the samples, facilitating the passage of radon and thus reducing the effectiveness of the sample as an anti-radon barrier.

3.2.2. Influence of thickness on radon mitigation effectiveness

In addition, it was decided to analyse the influence of paint coat thickness on the effectiveness of the paint layer as a barrier for radon mitigation. Effectiveness per unit of thickness was calculated as shown in equation (6), where net thickness was considered as the thickness of the paint without the neutral substrate, and net radon reduction percentage was determined by subtracting the reduction achieved by the filter paper alone to the radon reduction percentage with the sample painted. Table 7 presents the net paint layer thicknesses, the net radon reduction percentages, and the effectiveness values per unit thickness, calculated using Equation (6):

$$\text{Effectiveness per unit thickness} = \frac{\text{Net radon reduction (\%)}}{\text{Net paint layer thickness}} \cdot 100 \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

As shown in Table 7, the effectiveness per unit thickness ranges from 4.05 to 80.78 in the case of the commercial paint studied and reaches values of 349.43 for the anti-radon paint used as control. In the case of commercial paint, applying one or two coats shows low values in the effectiveness per unit thickness (4.05 and 17.53 % respectively). However, with the application of a third coat, substantial improvements are observed, reaching a net radon reduction percentage of 52.38 % and an efficacy per unit thickness of 70.58. As can be seen, the effectiveness per unit thickness increases with increasing number of coats, being the maximum for 4 coats of paint, where a value of 80.78 is achieved. This maximum effectiveness is achieved with a paint layer of 90 μm. Higher thickness increments (case of 5 layers and 100 μm) are less efficient than 4 coats due to the micro-cracks that occur in the paint layer adhered to the neutral substrate used.

Concerning its properties as an interior coating, vinyl paints are notable for their excellent adhesion on porous substrates such as concrete, plaster or mortar, adequate resistance to mould growth, durability and low cost (Novak and Ormsby, 2023). However, they aren't waterproof, and their adhesion on non-porous surfaces requires a previous coat of primer, which must be considered for their application.

With regard to the cost of applying this technique, taking into account the cost of the commercial paint (16 €/4 L) and its theoretical yield (16 m²/L of paint), the cost of painting a room to protect it from radon using this painting method with 4 coats would be 1.15 €/m² compared to the usual cost of painting an interior room that is usually covered with 2 coats to achieve a suitable decorative finish, which would cost 0.57 €/m². This is a low-cost solution to mitigate radon compared to other techniques such as the installation of general ventilation, which is also associated with a high energy cost for the operation of the mechanical extraction system.

3.3. Microscope images

Fig. 7 illustrates the images of samples composed of one to five coats of commercial water-based vinyl paint, acquired through optical microscopy at a magnification of 20X. It is observed that the paint is adhered to the substrate, forming a homogeneous and continuous coat in all cases, which explains its good capacity to reduce the radon

Fig. 7. Images of the surface finish of samples with one, two, three, four and five coats of paint obtained with the magnifying lens.

Fig. 8. Images of micro-cracks in the sample of five coats of paint obtained with the magnifying lens.

concentration passing through the neutral painted substrate.

Using an optical microscope at $20\times$ magnification, the surface of the paint samples was examined more precisely. In this analysis, micro-cracks were identified in the sample with five coats of paint (Fig. 8). The presence of these micro-cracks could be related to the lower effectiveness observed in this sample compared to the four-layer sample, especially in terms of radon reduction, where the percentage of radon reduction decreased by 16.10 %, from 82.25 % with four layers to 66.15 % with five layers. Furthermore, the formation of micro-cracks also significantly affects the radon resistance: while the four-layer sample has a resistance of 3.64 Ms/m, this is reduced to 1.64 Ms/m when an additional layer is applied.

Fig. 9 presents the profiles images obtained by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) for the filter paper samples coated

with one to five layers of commercial paint. All images were captured at $250\times$ magnification.

They show that the thickness of the paint layer on the neutral support increases progressively with the number of coats applied. Also, a greater penetration of the paint into the filter paper structure is observed as the number of layers increases, which could be related to the improvement of the results obtained in the samples with three and four layers of paint.

It seems that the initial layer of diluted paint homogenises the surface of the substrate, which allows better adhesion of the coats of paint subsequently applied to it. From a total thickness of $50\ \mu\text{m}$ (3 coats: one diluted and two undiluted), a significant effect on the radon mitigation capacity is observed.

Fig. 9. Profile images of filter paper samples with one, two, three, four, and five layers of paint obtained with FESEM microscopy.

4. Conclusions

The present study developed and evaluated a methodology for the application of a commercial indoor vinyl paint to reduce the radon concentration. The results show that a vinyl paint can be used to mitigate radon in indoor spaces, reaching a radon concentration reduction percentage of 82.25 %, and a diffusion coefficient of $7.48 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$.

Effectiveness increases with the number of coats applied, with a maximum of 4 coats. Micro-cracks have been observed after 5 coats, which could be due to the adhesion limit of the substrate used with the amount of paint applied.

The application for correct radon mitigation requires, according to the methodology developed, the application of a first coat diluted with 20 % water, followed by three additional coats of undiluted paint after each coat has dried. The initial coat of diluted paint prepares the surface of the substrate, which allows the other coats applied later to adhere better to the substrate.

Furthermore, the increase in the number of coats is proportional to the effectiveness per unit thickness, with the best results being achieved at thicknesses of 90 μm .

The results obtained represent a simple, easy and low-cost alternative to reduce radon exposure in interior spaces, since vinyl paints are the most commonly used for wall decoration. Moreover, it contributes to broaden the range of indoor radon mitigation solutions, especially in existing buildings.

In conclusion, this study provides substantial evidence of the effectiveness of paints as radon barriers and emphasises the necessity for further research to optimise their application over construction materials. The implementation of these measures has the potential to improve indoor air quality and represents an important contribution to public health by reducing the population exposure to radon. It is recommended that future research explore the long-term durability of these coatings and their behaviour under different environmental conditions to validate and expand on these findings.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

B. García-Gimeno: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **B. Ruvira:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **B. García-Fayos:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding

acquisition, Conceptualization. **J.M. Arnal:** Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **S.C. Cardona:** Formal analysis, Software, Validation. **G. Verdú:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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